

**TEACHERS' VARIABLES AS PREDICTORS OF EFFECTIVE INCLUSIVE CLASSROOM
INSTRUCTIONAL PRACTICES IN OWERRI MUNICIPAL, IMO STATE, NIGERIA**

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Abstract

This study investigated the relationship between teachers' variables (knowledge, attitudes, participation in conferences/workshops, and specialized training in inclusive education) and effective inclusive classroom instructional practices in Owerri Municipal in Imo State, Nigeria. The research aimed to examine the predictive power of these teacher-related factors on the implementation of effective inclusive instructional practices. A survey research design of correlational type was adopted for the study. The population consisted of 540 secondary school teachers from all six public secondary schools in the area. A sample of 162 teachers, representing 30% of the population, was selected through simple random sampling. The instrument used was the Teachers' Variables and Inclusive Classroom Instructional Practices Questionnaire (TVICIQ). The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach's Alpha, which yielded reliability coefficients ranging from 0.72 to 0.88. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to answer the research questions, while linear regression analysis and t-test statistics were employed to test the four null hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that teachers' variables are significant predictors of effective inclusive classroom instructional practices in Owerri Municipal, Imo State. Specifically, teachers' knowledge, attitudes, participation in conferences/workshops, and specialized training in inclusive education were found to be positively and significantly related to effective inclusive classroom instructional practices. Based on these findings, the researcher recommended that the federal and state governments should embark on school improvement programs by providing platforms for promoting inclusive practices at the school level. This could be achieved through systematic head teacher and teacher support programs, such as the organization of workshops and training sessions on inclusive education.

Keywords: Inclusion; Inclusive classroom; Instructional practices

Introduction

Education of persons with special needs is going inclusive after several years of exclusivist and separatist paradigm. Many factors combined to induce the shift in strategy. The United Nations' education campaigns and the paradigm change from defect to social model were foremost among them (Ozaji, 2018). The "within-child model," often known as the defect, is predicated on the idea that a child's deficiencies are primarily their own. On the other side, the social model is predicated on the idea that the child's disability is the result of society and its institutions (Okek-Oti, 2010). According to the social model, society and its institutions are oppressive, discriminatory, and disabling. If changes are to be made, the focus should be on removing barriers that prevent people with disabilities from participating fully in society and on altering the institutions, laws, and attitudes that foster and sustain exclusion (Mittler, 2000). According to Okeke-Oti (2010), inclusion is an educational strategy that de-emphasizes exclusion and places a focus on reorganising classrooms, schools, and teaching

methods to better suit the different needs of all students. The United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organisation provided a comprehensive definition of inclusion in 2021. It provided the following definition of inclusion:

“A process of addressing and responding to the diversity of needs of all learners through increasing participation in learning, cultures and communities and reducing exclusion within and from education. It involves changes and modifications in content, approaches, structures and strategies, with a common vision which covers all children of the appropriate age range and a conviction that it is the responsibilities of the regular system to educate all children”

Inclusive education is an approach that benefits all students, regardless of their disability or impairment. According to Okeke-Oti (2010), inclusion is the process of meeting the diverse needs of every student by encouraging their engagement in their local school and providing appropriate support.

Okuyibo (2001) defines inclusion as the placement of children with disabilities, regardless of the type or severity, in all general education settings - including classrooms, schools, and the wider community. The core tenet of inclusion, as per Okuyibo, is that children with disabilities should be fully integrated into the mainstream educational system. Ojogwu (2005) further emphasizes that inclusive education necessitates all students, regardless of disability or handicap, to receive education in the same classroom. This focus ensures that everyone in the community has an equal opportunity to benefit from formal education programs. Ozoji (2015) outlines three key facets of inclusive education: Allowing all students to fully engage in the activities and life of the mainstream setting. Ongoing efforts to remove obstacles preventing all learners from participating in education. The right to integrate into society at large and a shared effort to combat discrimination. Ozoji describes inclusive education as a curriculum or alternative specifically designed to teach students with a range of needs within the reorganized mainstream or school, helping them integrate into the school community. Similarly, the University of Bristol's Centre for Studies on Inclusive Education (2002) notes that inclusive education involves integrating all children, disabled or not, into regular preschool, school, college, and university programs with necessary support systems. While this research focuses on inclusive education for students with special needs, the researcher acknowledges that the concept extends beyond this group to include other marginalized child categories as well.

In an inclusive classroom setting, educators collaborate with students and other paraprofessionals to support each learner's unique educational objectives. Every student participates actively in the classroom activities, creating a dynamic learning environment (Onwubolu and Edozie, 2011). The authors describe an inclusive classroom as one where students primarily study and work in small groups, supporting and encouraging one another. It is a student-centered approach where students are highly accountable for the collective creative output of their community. Chukwu (2016) defines inclusive education as an approach that provides equal access to basic education in a regular classroom setting for all members of society. This suggests that regardless of their mental, physical, or any other condition, every individual has the right to pursue their preferred level of education alongside their able-bodied peers. In a community that values inclusion, a person's disability does not hinder them from participating in the same educational setting as others. Inclusion goes beyond merely placing a child with a disability in the classroom. It is an educational philosophy rooted in the conviction that every individual has an inherent right to fully engage in society (National Down Syndrome Society, 2012). Acceptance of diversity is thus enabled through inclusion.

An inclusive classroom environment is one that encourages and facilitates students of all abilities to learn in a variety of social and academic contexts. The decision to place a disabled child in a general education classroom rather than a mainstream or significantly separate setting is based on the determination that the child will

function better in the inclusive environment. For inclusion to be considered successful and effective, all educators and partners involved in the child's education must collaborate to enhance the child's learning and socialization. To ensure successful inclusive education, the New Jersey Council on Intellectual Disabilities (NJCIE, 2010) developed a quality indicator manual. This manual was created after a thorough analysis of existing literature and a study of similar documents that included indicators effectively applied to enhance inclusive teaching and learning methods in eight schools.

The NJCIE identified and pinpointed eleven key indicators for successful inclusive education:

Collaborative planning and teaching, Professional development, Individual student supports, Family-school partnerships, Leadership, School climate, Scheduling and participation, Curriculum, instruction, and assessment, Program planning and development, Program implementation, Program assessment.

These selected indicators were then assessed and tested in five different New Jersey school districts. This process served as both a reflective exercise and a tool for development, helping to identify the essential elements required to create an effective and inclusive environment. The manual also highlighted the importance of clear expectations set by teachers. It was found that teachers often lowered their expectations when students did not meet the expected social and behavioral standards, as these skills were not explicitly taught. The manual emphasized the need for teachers to set clear expectations to maximize learning and encourage student cohesion. To create a responsive classroom environment for all students, the manual recommended flexible grouping, peer support, and effective teaching strategies. These strategies include the regular use of routines, adjusted objectives and instruction, as well as a variety of formats, materials, and activities in inclusion classrooms. Overall, the NJCIE's quality indicator manual provides a comprehensive framework for developing and evaluating inclusive education practices, ensuring that the diverse needs of all students are met in the classroom. Teachers' characteristics play a crucial role in their ability to effectively handle all categories of children with special needs in inclusive classrooms. Successful inclusive instructional practices are directly dependent on the teachers and how they carry out their duties.

Teachers are the most important school-based factor, holding direct responsibility for shaping students' behavior and academic performance (Rockoff, 2004; Rivkin, Hanushek and Kain, 2005). It is therefore important to examine which specific teacher characteristics are related to effective inclusive classroom instructional practices. Understanding the teacher characteristics that produce the best inclusive classroom instructional outcomes can help schools identify unique ways to increase student performance using the available teacher resources. While excellence in academic life demands high levels of intelligence, recent studies have indicated that there are other factors that can predict academic performance, including teachers' characteristics (Busato et al., 2010; Chamorro-Premuzic and Furnham, 2013). Teachers play an instrumental role in the transfer of knowledge and cannot be overlooked in discussions of education. Research has shown a statistically significant relationship between teachers' characteristics and their students' academic performance (Ali, 2009). Driven by the goal of achieving proficient inclusive classroom teaching methodologies, this study aims to examine variables such as:

Teachers' knowledge, Teachers' attitudes, Teachers' participation in conferences/workshops, Teachers' specialized training in inclusive education and how these factors predict the effectiveness of inclusive classroom instructional practices. By identifying the key teacher characteristics that enable successful inclusive education, schools can better support and develop their teaching staff to ensure all students, including those with special needs, receive the highest quality of instruction. Teachers' knowledge on inclusive education refers to their awareness, information, and understanding about the concept, nature, justification, and processes involved in inclusive education. This knowledge is crucial, as the quality and quantity of teachers in an education system directly impact the instructional delivery and academic outcomes of students, inclusive education being no exception. With a strong knowledge base on inclusive education, teachers can set a positive

climate of responsibility, concern, and willingness to provide students with appropriate instructional delivery. Instructional practices are the tools and procedures that ease and provide equal access for all learners to actively participate in every classroom activity (Omede, 2016). A study by Ajuwon (2012) reported that teachers' knowledge of inclusive education and its application during assessment is important. Teachers without the requisite knowledge may abuse the purpose of inclusive education, especially during assessment, undermining the credibility and validity of the process. This, in turn, can negatively affect teachers' attitudes towards using inclusive classroom practices.

Elliott and Thurlow (2010) further emphasized that teachers' knowledge of inclusive classroom instructional practices, particularly on how to select materials that meet the varied instructional and other needs of learners, is indispensable. Apart from teachers' knowledge, another critical factor that may predict effective inclusive classroom instructional practices is teachers' attitudes. Positive teacher attitudes, stemming from a strong understanding of inclusive education, are essential for creating an environment where all students can thrive. By examining these key teacher characteristics, including knowledge and attitudes, schools can better support and develop their teaching staff to ensure inclusive education is implemented successfully, providing the highest quality of instruction for all students. The concept of attitude in special needs education is as old as the field itself. The relationship between attitudes and the provision of education and related services to learners with special needs has been a focus of extensive research. Attitude is a psychological construct that determines one's response to something, an event, situation, or a person. It is an individual disposition characterized by beliefs, thoughts, and emotions or feelings towards an object.

In the Nigerian context, teachers' attitudes towards special education have evolved through different developmental stages, ranging from extermination, sanction, vocation, and finally, education (Ikpaye, 2019). This suggests that teachers' attitudes and the progress in special education have been closely intertwined. Ozoji (2005) further distinguishes between traditional and scientific attitudes towards disabilities. Traditional attitudes are characterized by the belief that disability is a punishment or reward for the wrongdoings of parents, while scientific attitudes acknowledge that disability is the product of various factors that can be understood through scientific inquiry. Teachers' attitudes can pose a significant limitation for the success of inclusive education. The findings of this study align with previous research on the importance of teachers' attitudes towards inclusive education. For example, Omede (2016) concluded that many teachers are skeptical about the viability of inclusive education arrangements in regular schools. Similarly, a study in Sokoto State, Nigeria, found that while teachers were enthusiastic and skilled in using effective teaching methods, many had negative attitudes towards students with special needs and low expectations of their abilities. If teachers do not have positive attitudes towards learners with special needs, it is unlikely that these children will receive satisfactory education. For a child with a disability to benefit maximally from inclusion, it is crucial that general education teachers be able to teach a wide array of children, including those with varying disabilities. Some disabilities may require teachers with specialized training, such as in the use of braille or sign language. Therefore, in addition to the recommendations made, the researcher should also emphasize the need for comprehensive teacher training programs that instill positive attitudes and equip teachers with the necessary skills to effectively include students with diverse learning needs in their classrooms.

Avramidis and Norwich (2010) further found that teachers' attitudes towards inclusionary practices were influenced by the nature and severity of the disability, as well as the availability of accommodations and support services. Positive teacher attitudes, coupled with the necessary resources and training, are essential for the successful implementation of inclusive education.

Specialized training is another key factor that can predict the effectiveness of inclusive classroom instructional practices. Teaching in an inclusive classroom is quite demanding, as each child has unique educational needs that require tailored strategies. This implies that teachers should undergo specialized training or preparation to

equip them with the necessary knowledge, skills, and attitudes for this task. As Ruzena (2005) notes, teaching individuals with learning disabilities requires formal and specialized preparation. Such training should aim to build a strong theoretical understanding of special needs education, as well as concrete pedagogical skills. Osurji's (2013) study on the post-training competency of teachers in public schools in Jos, Nigeria, found that teachers whose formal training was in specific learning disabilities were more competent in teaching learners with dysgraphia. These teachers were also better able to educate parents on current trends in the education of children with special needs. Similarly, Ogbonna's (2015) research assessed the relationship between teachers' specialization and the use of technology accommodations in special schools in North Central Nigeria. The results indicated a strong positive correlation, suggesting that specialized training is necessary to meet the instructional needs of learners with handwriting disorders.

In a related study, the Learning Disabilities Center Jos (2013) examined teachers' performance in inclusive schools in Northeast Nigeria. The findings revealed that teachers without formal and specialized training in specific learning disabilities were unable to identify the characteristics of dysgraphia or differentiate the learning needs of children with these disabilities. This led to the exclusion of learners from the learning process, indicating a lack of adequate teacher preparation for the diverse inclusive school population. Further assessment showed that special education teachers in the zone who specialized in visual and hearing impairments lacked adequate knowledge about other disabilities. In contrast, in the United States, specialized training is emphasized to equip special education teachers to work in different settings and with a variety of special needs children. For instance, the University of Oregon College of Education, like many universities in the USA, runs a robust special education training program that focuses on both theory and practice, exposing teachers to real experiences of working with children with special needs in their classrooms (John, 2016). The evidence clearly suggests that specialized training is a crucial factor in enabling teachers to effectively implement inclusive classroom instructional practices and meet the diverse needs of all learners. In the context of this discourse, teachers' participation in conferences and workshops is conceived as a formal meeting of professional teachers who come together to discuss, share, and exchange their research findings on various topics within a broader theme. These events are typically academic in nature and organized by educational institutions or organizations. On the other hand, workshops are training or capacity-building meetings that emphasize improving the knowledge and skills of teachers to enhance their functional ability in instructional processes. Both of these activities or events are of paramount importance for the continued development and effectiveness of teachers, particularly when teaching in inclusive classrooms. Research has shown that the best or current strategies for educating students in inclusive classrooms are often discovered through research. One of the ways to disseminate such findings is through conferences and workshops. This is why Hill's (2012) study on the value of workshops for teachers, including those teaching in inclusive classrooms, concludes that the most effective teachers are those who go beyond the call of duty and textbook knowledge to engage in continued participation in conferences and workshops.

The findings indicate that conferences and workshops, as strategies for continuing education, offer teachers the opportunity to be exposed to knowledge and skills that were not possible to learn during their initial professional course of study. This is particularly relevant for the subject matter of the present study, as most teachers have only heard about the concept of inclusive education in recent years. Conferences and workshops can, therefore, expose them to technology-based learning that requires specific skills and competencies for proper utilization in the instructional process. Given the significance of these professional development opportunities, it is imperative for schools in Nigeria to encourage and sponsor teachers, especially those concerned with inclusive education, to participate in such training activities. This will enable them to integrate technology-based learning into their classroom instruction, build their confidence, and develop the leadership skills necessary for 21st-century education and beyond.

According to the National Association for Exceptional Children, as cited in Busato et al. (2015), an evaluation of the impact of their workshops on teachers' professional competence reported that more than 200 teachers teaching children with special needs in schools across the South-South geopolitical zone of Nigeria have been empowered with skills to integrate common and low-technology into their pedagogical processes. Furthermore, the Cross River State Ministry of Education's (2012) survey report indicates that teachers' ongoing professional development has been a priority. The report shows that 300, 546, 358, and 671 special education teachers participated in retraining workshops organized in collaboration with the State Universal Basic Education Board (SUBEB) in 2008, 2009, 2010, and 2011 respectively. The thematic areas covered in these workshops ranged from inclusive practices to technology accommodations for children with disabilities. In a similar research study, a content and product comparative evaluation found that teachers who were exposed to training on emerging themes in specific learning disabilities, such as collaborative teaching, ICT, accommodation strategies, and accountability in special needs education, showed improvements in managing learners with specific learning disabilities (SLD) compared to those without such knowledge and skills (Ozzeh, 2015; Robinson, 2013).

Richard (2008) reported that teachers who participate in online training, such as e-conferences, workshops, and seminars, have the opportunity to interact with experts in various aspects of disabilities without incurring significant costs. Fareo (2013) further highlighted that national conferences, workshops, and seminars are considered the best strategies to reposition teachers for better service delivery, especially to those with disabilities. The evidence clearly demonstrates the significant impact that teachers' participation in conferences, workshops, and other professional development activities can have on their ability to effectively support students with special needs in inclusive classrooms. These opportunities allow teachers to acquire the necessary knowledge, skills, and strategies to create inclusive learning environments that cater to the diverse needs of all learners.

Statement of the Problem

Inclusive education, concerned with providing a system of education that offers every member of society equal opportunity to acquire basic education in the regular school environment, is not achieving its expected objectives due to poor teachers' characteristics. The public perception is that teachers' standards and competencies have declined, rendering them unable to effectively boost their teaching abilities, leading to poor performance. However, the underlying issue appears to be that teachers lack the requisite characteristics needed to discharge their duties in the implementation of effective inclusive classroom instructional practices. The failures of inclusive classroom instructional practices can be attributed to diverse factors. Evidence from the literature suggests that one of the essential determinants of success or failure in inclusive education is the teachers' variables. However, previous works available to the researchers have not focused on the specific teachers' variables, including their knowledge, attitudes, participation in conferences/workshops, and specialized training in inclusive education, and how these factors predict the effectiveness of inclusive classroom instructional practices.

Given this gap in the research, education stakeholders need to have a deeper understanding of these teachers' variables to ensure effective inclusive classroom instructional practices. It is against this backdrop that the problem of this study was posed in the form of a research question: To what extent do teachers' variables predict effective inclusive classroom instructional practices in Owerri Municipal, Imo State. By examining the specific teachers' characteristics that enable or hinder the success of inclusive education, this study aims to provide valuable insights that can guide policymakers, school administrators, and teacher training programs in developing strategies to support and empower teachers in delivering effective inclusive classroom instruction. Addressing this critical issue is essential for ensuring that the inclusive education system achieves its intended objectives and provides equal educational opportunities for all members of society.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to investigate teachers' variables as predictors of effective inclusive classroom instructional practices in Owerri Municipal, Imo State. Specifically the study sought to:

1. Determine the extent teachers' knowledge predicts effective inclusive classroom instructional practices in Owerri Municipal, Imo State.
2. Ascertain the extent teachers' attitude predict effective inclusive classroom instructional practices in Owerri Municipal, Imo State.
3. Determine the extent teachers' specialized training predicts effective inclusive classroom instructional practices in Owerri Municipal, Imo State.
4. Ascertain the extent teachers' participation in conferences/workshops predicts effective inclusive classroom instructional practices in Owerri Municipal, Imo State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study

1. To what extent does teachers' knowledge predict effective inclusive classroom instructional practices in Owerri Municipal, Imo State?
2. What is the extent teachers' attitude predicts effective inclusive classroom instructional practices in Owerri Municipal, Imo State?
3. To what extent does teachers' specialized training predict effective inclusive classroom instructional practices in Owerri Municipal, Imo State?
4. What is the extent teachers' participation in conferences/workshops predict effective inclusive classroom instructional practices in Owerri Municipal, Imo State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses (H_0) were postulated to guide the study and tested at 0.05 levels of significance:

H₀₁: Teachers' knowledge does not significantly predict effective inclusive classroom instructional practices in Owerri Municipal, Imo State.

H₀₂: Teachers' attitude do not significantly predict effective inclusive classroom instructional practices in Owerri Municipal, Imo State.

H₀₃: Teachers' specialized training does not significantly predict effective inclusive classroom instructional practices in Owerri Municipal, Imo State.

H₀₄: Teachers' participation in conferences/workshops does not significantly predict effective inclusive classroom instructional practices in Owerri Municipal, Imo State.

Methodology

The study employed a correlational survey research design, which was considered suitable as it allowed the researchers to investigate the magnitude and direction (positive or negative) of the relationship between teachers' variables (independent variables) and effective inclusive classroom instructional practices (dependent variable). This design enabled the researchers to determine the predictive power of the teachers' variables on the outcome variable. The study was conducted in Owerri Municipal, Imo State, with a population of 540 secondary school teachers across six public secondary schools. A sample of 162 teachers, representing 30% of the population, was selected using simple random sampling. The instrument used was the Teachers' Variables

and Inclusive Classroom Instructional Practices Questionnaire (TVICIQ), which had two sections: Section A for demographic data and Section B for eliciting information on the variables of interest. The instrument was structured on a 4-point Likert-type scale and had a total of 51 items. The validity and reliability of the instrument were established, with Cronbach's Alpha yielding reliability coefficient indices ranging from 0.72 to 0.88. The data was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson r) was employed to determine the direction and magnitude of the relationships. Linear regression analysis and t-test statistics were used to test the null hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance.

The interpretation of the correlation coefficients was based on Cohen's guidelines: 0.00 - 0.20 = very low/no relationship, 0.20 – 0.40 = low, 0.40 – 0.60 = moderate, 0.60 – 0.80 = high, and 0.80 – 1.00 = very high. For the hypotheses testing, the null hypotheses were rejected when the associated probability value (p-value) was less than the significant level of 0.05, and accepted when the p-value was greater than 0.05.

Results

Research Question 1

To what extent does teachers’ knowledge predict effective inclusive classroom instructional practices in Owerri Municipal, Imo State?

Table 1: Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation Analysis on extent Teachers’ Knowledge Predicts Effective Inclusive Classroom Instructional Practices

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.362 ^a	.131	.128	3.44778

a. Predictors: (Constant), Teachers’ Knowledge

Result on Table 1 showed that the relationship between teachers’ knowledge and effective inclusive classroom instructional practices is 0.362 with a coefficient of determination of 0.131. This coefficient of determination indicates that 13.1% of teachers’ knowledge accounted for the variation in effective inclusive classroom instructional practices. This infers that there exists a positive relationship between teachers’ knowledge and effective inclusive classroom instructional practices but the relationship was low.

Research Question 2

What is the extent teachers’ attitude predict effective inclusive classroom instructional practices in Owerri Municipal, Imo State?

Table 2: Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation Analysis on Extent Teachers’ Attitudes Predict Effective Inclusive Classroom Instructional Practices

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.843 ^a	.710	.709	1.99224

a. Predictors: (Constant), Teachers’ Attitudes

The result on Table 2 indicated that the relationship between teachers' attitude and effective inclusive classroom instructional practices is 0.843 with a coefficient of determination of 0.710. This coefficient of determination indicates that 71% of teachers' attitudes accounted for the variation in effective inclusive classroom instructional practices. This means that there exists a positive relationship between teachers' attitudes and effective inclusive classroom instructional practices and the relationship was very high.

Research Question 3

To what extent does teachers' specialized training predict effective inclusive classroom instructional practices in Owerri Municipal, Imo State?

Table 3: Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Analysis on Extent Teachers' Specialized Training Predict Effective Inclusive Classroom Instructional Practices

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.392 ^a	.154	.151	3.40263

a. Predictors: (Constant), Teachers' Specialized Training

The result on Table 3 revealed that the relationship between teachers' specialized training and effective inclusive classroom instructional practices is 0.392 with a coefficient of determination of 0.154. This coefficient of determination indicates that 15.4% of teachers' specialized training accounted for the variation in effective inclusive classroom instructional practices. This means that there exists a positive relationship between teachers' specialized training and effective inclusive classroom instructional practices but the relationship was low.

Research Question 4

What is the extent teachers' participation in conferences/workshops predicts effective inclusive classroom instructional practices in Owerri Municipal, Imo State?

Table 4: Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Analysis on Extent Teachers' Participation in Conferences/Workshops Predict Effective Inclusive Classroom Instructional Practices

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.445 ^a	.199	.057	3.58600

a. Predictors: (Constant), Teachers' Participation in Conferences/Workshops

Result on Table 4 showed that the correlation between teachers' participation in conferences/workshops and effective inclusive classroom instructional practices is 0.445 with a coefficient of determination of 0.199. This coefficient of determination indicates that, 19.9% of teachers' participation in conferences/workshops accounted for the variation in effective inclusive classroom instructional practices. This indicates that there exists a positive relationship between teachers' participation in conferences/workshops and effective inclusive classroom instructional practices and the relationship was moderate.

H₀₁: Teachers’ knowledge does not significantly predict effective inclusive classroom instructional practices in Owerri Municipal, Imo State.

Table 5: Linear Regression Analysis on Teachers’ Knowledge as Predictor of Effective Inclusive Classroom Instructional Practices

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	t-cal	Sig.	Decision
1	Regression	580.562	1	580.562	24.118	6.989	.000 ^b	Reject H ₀₁
	Residual	3851.453	160	24.071				
	Total	4432.015	161					

a. Dependent Variable: Effective inclusive classroom instructional practices

b. Predictors: (Constant), Teachers’ Knowledge

The results presented in Table 5 of the study revealed that teachers' knowledge significantly predicts effective inclusive classroom instructional practices. This is evidenced by the following:

The F-value of 24.118 was found to be statistically significant at the 0.000 level, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance.

The calculated t-value of 6.989 was also found to be statistically significant at the 0.000 level, which is again less than the 0.05 level of significance.

Based on these findings, the null hypothesis that "teachers' knowledge does not significantly predict effective inclusive classroom instructional practices" was rejected. The alternate hypothesis, which states that "teachers' knowledge is a significant predictor of effective inclusive classroom instructional practices in Owerri Municipal, Imo State," was therefore accepted. In other words, the results indicate that teachers' knowledge plays a significant role in determining the effectiveness of inclusive classroom instructional practices. The better the teachers' knowledge, the more likely they are to implement effective inclusive instructional practices in their classrooms.

H₀₂: Teachers’ attitudes do not significantly predict effective inclusive classroom instructional practices in Owerri Municipal, Imo State.

Table 6: Linear Regression Analysis on Teachers’ Attitudes as Predictor of Effective Inclusive Classroom Instructional Practices

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	t-cal.	Sig.	Decision
1	Regression	3146.050	1	3146.050	120.698	28.154	.000b	Reject H ₀₂
	Residual	1285.965	160	24.071				

Total 4432.015 161

a. Dependent Variable: Effective inclusive classroom instructional practices

b. Predictors: (Constant), Teachers’ Attitudes

The results presented in Table 6 of the study revealed that teachers' attitude significantly predicts effective inclusive classroom instructional practices. Specifically: The F-value of 120.698 was found to be statistically significant at the 0.000 level, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance.

The calculated t-value of 28.154 was also found to be statistically significant at the 0.000 level, which is again less than the 0.05 level of significance. Based on these findings, the null hypothesis that "teachers' attitude does not significantly predict effective inclusive classroom instructional practices" was rejected. The alternate hypothesis, which states that "teachers' attitude is a significant predictor of effective inclusive classroom instructional practices in Owerri Municipal, Imo State," was therefore accepted. These results indicate that teachers' attitudes play a crucial role in determining the effectiveness of inclusive classroom instructional practices. More positive and supportive attitudes among teachers are associated with more effective implementation of inclusive instructional strategies in the classroom.

H₀₃: Teachers’ specialized training does not significantly predict effective inclusive classroom instructional practices in Owerri Municipal, Imo State.

Table 7: Linear Regression Analysis on Teachers’ Specialized Training as Predictor of Effective Inclusive Classroom Instructional Practices

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	t-cal.	Sig.	Decision
Regression	680.779	1	680.779	29.037	7.668	.000 ^b	Reject H ₀₅
Residual	3751.236	160	23.445				
Total	4432.015	161					

a. Dependent Variable: Effective inclusive classroom instructional practices

b. Predictors: (Constant), Teachers’ Specialized Training

The result on Table 7 revealed that teachers’ specialized training significantly predicts effective inclusive classroom instructional practices. This is shown by the F- value of 29.037, which is significant at 0.000 level, and also significant at 0.05 level of probability. This is further shown by the calculated t value of 7.668, which is also significant at .000 and at 0.05 level. Therefore, the null hypothesis that teachers’ specialized training does not significantly predict effective inclusive classroom instructional practices is rejected and the alternate hypothesis upheld. Thus, teachers’ specialized training is a significant predictor of effective inclusive classroom instructional practices in Owerri Municipal, Imo State.

H₀₄: Teachers’ participation in conferences/workshops does not significantly predict effective inclusive classroom instructional practices in Owerri Municipal, Imo State.

Table 8: Linear Regression Analysis on Teachers’ Participation in Conferences/Workshops as Predictor of Effective Inclusive Classroom Instructional Practices

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	t-cal	Sig.	Decision
1	Regression	265.574	1	265.574	10.198	4.544	.000 ^b Reject H ₀₆
	Residual	4166.441	160	26.040			
	Total	4432.015	161				

a. Dependent Variable: Effective inclusive classroom instructional practices

b. Predictors: (Constant), Teachers’ participation in conferences/workshops

The result on Table 8 revealed that teachers’ participation in conferences/workshops significantly predicts effective inclusive classroom instructional practices. This is shown by the F- value of 10.198, which is significant at 0.000 level also significant at 0.05 level of probability. This is further shown by the calculated t value of 4.544, which is also significant at .000 and at 0.05 level. Therefore, the null hypothesis that teachers’ participation in conferences/workshops does not significantly predict effective inclusive classroom instructional practices is rejected and the alternate hypothesis upheld. Thus, teachers’ participation in conferences/workshops is a significant predictor of effective inclusive classroom instructional practices in Owerri Municipal, Imo State.

Discussion of Findings

The findings from research question one, as presented in Table 1, revealed a positive but low relationship between teachers' knowledge and effective inclusive classroom instructional practices. This finding was possible because the coefficient of determination associated with the correlation coefficient was positive, indicating that teachers' knowledge accounted for some of the variation in effective inclusive classroom instructional practices. This finding aligns with the work of Ajuwon (2012), who found that teachers' knowledge of the types of accommodations needed by children and the process of evaluating the success or failure of inclusive education is crucial. Ajuwon further reported that teachers without the requisite knowledge often abuse the purpose of inclusive education, especially during assessment, causing the process to lose its credibility and validity. The hypothesis testing results in Table 5 showed that teachers' knowledge is a significant predictor of effective inclusive classroom instructional practices in Owerri Municipal, Imo State. This was possible because the F-value associated with the linear regression was significant, as the probability value was less than the alpha level. This finding is supported by the view of Elliott and Thurlow (2010), who opined that teachers' knowledge of inclusive classroom instructional practices, particularly in selecting appropriate materials that meet the varied instructional and other needs of learners, is indispensable.

In summary, while the relationship between teachers' knowledge and effective inclusive classroom instructional practices was positive but low, the study findings indicate that teachers' knowledge is a significant predictor of the effectiveness of inclusive classroom instructional practices. This highlights the importance of ensuring teachers have the necessary knowledge and skills to support the implementation of inclusive education.

The summary of data analysis for research question 2, as presented in Table 2, indicates that there was a positive and very high relationship between teachers' attitudes and effective inclusive classroom instructional practices. This finding is possible because the teachers' attitudes and effective inclusive classroom instructional practices scores were correlated, and the correlation coefficient obtained was positive. Furthermore, the hypothesis testing results shown in Table 6 reveal that teachers' attitudes significantly predict effective inclusive

classroom instructional practices in Owerri Municipal, Imo State. This implies that many teachers are skeptical about the workability of inclusive education arrangements in regular schools.

The above finding is in line with the study conducted by Avramidis and Norwich (2010), who examined teachers' attitudes towards inclusionary practices. They found that while the teachers' attitudes were generally positive, they were strongly influenced by the nature and severity of the disability, as well as the availability of accommodations and support services.

This suggests that teachers' skepticism about the viability of inclusive education in regular school settings can negatively impact the implementation of effective inclusive classroom instructional practices. The very high positive relationship between teachers' attitudes and the effectiveness of inclusive practices underscores the importance of addressing teachers' attitudes towards inclusive education to ensure its successful implementation.

By understanding the factors that shape teachers' attitudes, such as the availability of necessary accommodations and support services, policymakers and school administrators can develop targeted interventions to foster more positive and receptive attitudes among teachers. This, in turn, can contribute to the creation of inclusive learning environments that effectively cater to the diverse needs of all students.

The evidence obtained in this study, as presented in Table 3, revealed a positive but low relationship between teachers' specialized training and effective inclusive classroom instructional practices. This is because the coefficient of determination associated with the correlation coefficient was positive, indicating that teachers' specialized training accounted for some of the variation in effective inclusive classroom instructional practices.

Hypothesis 3 further revealed that teachers' specialized training significantly predicts effective inclusive classroom instructional practices. This finding is supported by the understanding that teaching in an inclusive classroom is quite demanding, as each child has unique educational needs that require specialized strategies. This implies that teachers should undergo special training or preparation to be equipped with the necessary knowledge, skills, and attitudes for this task.

The findings of this study align with the work of Osurji (2013), who discovered that teachers whose formal training was in specific learning disabilities were more competent in teaching learners with dysgraphia. Similarly, the findings agree with Ogbonna's (2015) study, which found a strong positive correlation between teachers' specialized training and the ability to meet the instructional needs of learners with handwriting disorders.

Furthermore, the Learning Disabilities Center Jos (2013) survey of teachers' performance in inclusive schools in Northeast Nigeria found that teachers without formal and specialized training in specific learning disabilities were unable to identify the characteristics of dysgraphia or differentiate the learning requirements of children with these impairments.

These findings underscore the importance of teachers' specialized training in enabling them to effectively implement inclusive classroom instructional practices and meet the diverse needs of all learners. While the relationship between specialized training and effective inclusive practices was positive but low, the study results indicate that specialized training is a significant predictor of success in inclusive education settings. By ensuring that teachers receive the necessary specialized training and preparation, schools and education systems can better equip their teachers to create inclusive learning environments that cater to the unique needs of each student, ultimately enhancing the effectiveness of inclusive classroom instructional practices.

A moderate positive relationship has been found between teachers' participation in conferences and workshops and effective inclusive classroom instructional methods, according to the summary of data analysis for research

question four in Table 4. The positive correlation coefficient made this conclusion attainable. Furthermore, Table 8's result showed that the probability value is smaller than the alpha level, indicating that the linear regression's F-value is significant. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected. This suggests that teachers' participation in conferences/workshops significantly predict effective inclusive classroom instructional practices in Owerri Municipal of Imo State. This is true because conferences/workshops will expose them to the technology-based learning that require skills and competences for proper utilization in instructional process. This finding is in agreement with earlier finding of Hill (2012) who studied the value of workshops for teachers, including those teaching in an inclusive classroom and discovered that great and effective teachers are those who go beyond call to duty and textbook to continued participation in conferences and workshops. He further found that conferences and workshops as strategies for continuing education offer extra opportunity to be exposed to knowledge and skills that were not possible learnt during professional courses of study.

Conclusion

The findings of the study revealed that teachers' variables are significant predictors of effective inclusive classroom instructional practices in Owerri Municipal, Imo State, based on teachers' knowledge, teachers' attitudes teachers' participation in conferences/ workshops, teachers' specialized training in inclusive education.

Recommendations

1. Teachers should be provided with training to build their basic knowledge and skills in special education instructional tasks. Novice teachers should not be assigned to inclusive education schools as their primary responsibilities.
2. The school community, including students and teachers, should work to build positive attitudes towards inclusiveness. This involves promoting a non-segregated system of education that is accessible to all children regardless of their economic, health, or social status.
3. The Federal Government should prioritize inclusive education policies. This includes establishing clear criteria for personnel training and coordinating the special education unit to create awareness and direct inclusive education efforts towards goal achievement.
4. Head teachers and teachers should be encouraged to promote inclusive education by actively participating in conferences, seminars, and workshops related to this topic.
5. The recommendations emphasize the need for comprehensive teacher training, positive school culture, supportive government policies, and continuous professional development to enable effective implementation of inclusive classroom practices. By addressing these key areas, the study suggests that schools can make meaningful progress in creating truly inclusive learning environments.

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TEACHERS' VARIABLES AND INCLUSIVE CLASSROOM INSTRUCTIONAL PRACTICES QUESTIONNAIRE (TVICIQ)

Dear Participant,

This questionnaire is to illicit response on teachers' variables as predictors of effective inclusive classroom instructional practices in Owerri Municipal, Imo State. Please kindly express your opinion, it would be treated confidentially and only for academic purpose. The questionnaire is divided into two parts.

Part A: Personal data

Instruction: Please check (√) as applicable to you.

Gender: Male [] Female []

Educational Qualification: NCE [] B.Ed. [] M.Ed. PhD []

Teaching Experience: 0-5 [] 6-10 [] 11 and above []

Number of conferences/workshops in special education attended in the last ten years

0-5 [] 6-15 [] 16 and above []

Section B

Part I Instruction: You are humbly requested to check (√) these statements as the best apply to you using strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D) Strongly Disagreed (SD)

S/N	Statements	SA	A	D	SD
	Teachers' knowledge				
1.	Knowledge about the concept of inclusive education influences effective inclusive classroom instructional practices.				
2.	When you know the different processes of inclusive education it helps you to properly in teaching learners with special needs.				
3.	Selection and appropriate use of instructional practices in teaching these diverse learners depends on your knowledge.				
4.	Knowing how to evaluate Instructional practices in an inclusive classroom contribute to its appropriate usage in teaching.				
5.	Being aware of reasons/importance of inclusive education is necessary for effective utilization				
6.	Knowledge of policy/rules on inclusive education is not important in teaching learners with special needs.				
7.	Knowing how to allow frequent breaks during instruction, test, and examination is not necessary in inclusive classroom.				
8.	The knowledge of choice of appropriate materials does not influence effective inclusive classroom instructional practices				
9.	Knowledge of curriculum does not enhance the effective inclusive classroom instructional practices.				
	Teachers' Attitude				
10.	I appreciate the concept of inclusive education.				
11.	I feel bad when I see abled and non-abled learners in the same classroom				
12.	When learners with special needs learn in the same classroom, I feel happy.				
13.	I can spend my time or money to support inclusive classroom instructional practices.				
14.	I do not look down on learners with special needs.				
15.	Every learner has his/her own challenge so there is nothing important about inclusive classroom.				
16.	Frequent breaks during instruction/evaluation are abuse of teaching – learning process.				
17.	Allowing learners with special needs to make a choice of setting for instruction/evaluation is a malpractice in the school system.				
18.	I am angry when learners with special needs are allowed to assistive technology during instructional practice.				
19.	Allowing learners with special needs to alone or in-group is mark of encouraging laziness and reduce the standard and value.				

Teachers' participation in conferences/workshops					
20.	Participation in conferences/workshops enhances effective inclusive classroom instructional practices.				
21.	All forms of participation improves teachers' ability in inclusive classroom instructional practices				
22.	Chairing a panel or roundtable sessions improves one's ability to implement inclusive classroom instructional practices				
23.	Being a repertoire in a panel build teachers' ability to practice inclusive classroom instruction				
24.	Presenting papers in conferences improves my efficiency teaching and using instructional accommodations with learners with special needs				
25.	Attending conferences with or without presenting papers is not important to me.				
26.	Participating in writing a communiqué after the conference does not improves ability to practice inclusive classroom instruction.				
27.	I do not attend workshops because they are meaningless to me.				
28.	Being member of conference/workshop planning committee does not influence my ability to practice inclusiveness.				
29.	Attending plenary session of conferences is a waste of time to me.				
Teachers' specialized training					
30.	Training on professional practice of inclusive classroom is every necessary for it proper use in teaching learners with disability.				
31.	Training on technology-based instruction improves their utilization by teachers in teaching learners with special needs in an inclusive classroom.				
32.	Training on development of inclusiveness for learners with special needs also helps in their utilization in teaching.				
33.	Training in the nature, type, characteristics and manifestation of special needs is important in the choice of instructional strategies.				
34.	Majoring on specific learning disorders as field of study is the basis for being able practices inclusive classroom instruction.				
35.	Training on the use of flexible grouping /peer supports helps me to ensure that professional practice and standards are maintained.				
36.	Every teacher can correctly use instructional accommodations for learners with dysgraphia.				
37.	You do not need any special training to be able evaluate the effectiveness of inclusiveness as basis for review.				
38.	Training on policy, rules and professional ethics on the practice of inclusiveness is waste of resources.				

39.	Training on how to involve parents in inclusive educational process is not necessary because they are not teachers.				
Inclusive Classroom Instructional Practices					
40.	Inclusion student sits separate from class without instructional aid.				
41.	Peer supports is always encouraging				
42.	There is rule creation.				
43.	I frequently use yelling/negative comments such as just forget it, sit down.				
44.	I always use encouraging comments such as you can do it mentality.				
45.	I maintain a calm/controlled attitude.				
46.	I promote student socialization.				
47.	I always plan my lessons.				
48.	I always incorporate visual, tactile and kinesthetic materials and activities to meet a variety of learners' needs				
49.	I frequently use class-wide routines and procedures to support classroom management and learning.				
50.	I always modify curricular goals and classroom instruction using the same or similar, age appropriate materials for assignments, homework and tests.				
51.	I always use multiple formats to provide instruction such as individual, pairs, small groups and whole class.				